

DEHYDROGENATIVE SILANE COUPLING ON POROUS SILICON

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SUMMARY

Organic hydridosilanes can be grafted to hydrogen-terminated porous Si nanostructures without the use of a catalyst. The reaction proceeds efficiently with mild heating on the benchtop, and it shows little sensitivity to air or water impurities. The resulting modified surfaces are stable to corrosive aqueous solutions and common organic solvents.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon directly bonded to crystalline silicon yields a very stable surface species. First recognized by Chidsey in the early 1990s, Si-C bonded species possess greater kinetic stability relative to Si-O due to the low electronegativity of carbon. Silicon can readily form 5- and 6-coordinate intermediates, and an electronegative element such as oxygen enhances the tendency of silicon to be attacked by nucleophiles. The most ubiquitous reaction used to form a Si-C bond to hydrogen-terminated porous silicon is hydrosilylation, a reaction first demonstrated by Buriak and elaborated by Boukherroub, and many others. Hydrosilylation involves addition of Si-H across a C-C double or triple bond. The C-C multiple bond of the alkene (C-C double bond) or alkyne (C-C triple bond) is usually at one end of the hydrocarbon chain, a so-called terminal bond. On porous silicon, the reaction is promoted by heat, light, mechanical scribing, or by Lewis acid catalysis. The main requirement of the reaction is that the surface contains Si-H species so they can react with the alkene or alkyne. Thus it is important to use freshly etched porous silicon and to exclude oxygen and water from the reaction mixture.

Here we report a mild surface modification method using alkyl-hydridosilanes via thermally induced dehydrogenative coupling reactions and formation of self-assembled monolayers on the oxide-free silicon surface. The chemisorption of alkyl-hydridosilanes on silicon appears more likely when silicon has the ability to adsorb or coordinate with hydrogen. It is proposed that the key step in chemisorption of hydridosilanes involves dissociative-adsorption of the alkyl-hydridosilane with either the release of hydrogen or hydrogen absorption by the silicon substrate.

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Preparation of p-type porous silicon (pSi) nanostructure.

Layers of mesoporous silicon were electrochemically etched into heavily boron-doped ($<1 \text{ m}\Omega\text{-cm}$ resistivity) single crystal silicon wafers in a Teflon etch cell that exposed 8.04 cm^2 of the polished Si wafer surface, using a platinum coil counter electrode with a 3:1 (v:v) 48% aqueous HF: absolute ethanol mixture. The Si wafers were contacted on the backside with a strip of Al foil. The etch cell was thoroughly rinsed and fresh HF electrolyte was added. Samples were then prepared by etching at constant current density of different values depending on the sample porosity desired.

Preparation of n-type porous silicon (pSi) nanostructure.

Photoluminescent pSi samples were prepared from n-type wafers ($<100>$, $0.8 \Omega\text{-cm}$ resistivity) with front side illumination (tungsten halogen lamp, 60 mW/cm^2) in 1:1 (v:v) 48% aqueous HF: absolute ethanol electrolyte. The etch cell was thoroughly rinsed and fresh HF electrolyte was added. Samples were etched at a constant current density of 50 mA/cm^2 for 10 min.

Coupling reaction with hydridosilane on pSi nanostructure.

The freshly etched pSi samples, either p or n-type, were immersed in neat hydridosilane reagent in a vial. The vial was capped, partially immersed in an oil bath and maintained at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hr. The chip was removed and rinsed with *n*-hexane and ethanol several times and then dried in a stream of dry nitrogen. To remove traces of physically absorbed reagent and/or side products, some samples were further rinsed by immersion in *n*-hexane, which was then subjected to ultra-sonication. Additional rinsing to remove oxides or oxide-trapped reagents involved thorough rinsing with a mixture of 3:1 (v:v) of aqueous 49% HF and absolute ethanol.

ATR-FTIR spectra of coupling products were recorded using a Thermo Scientific Nicolet 6700 FTIR instrument fitted with a Smart iTR diamond ATR fixture. ATR-FTIR spectrum of the product (Fig. 1a) displayed bands associated with the organosilane: C-H stretching and bending vibrations, and two strong bands around 1000 cm^{-1} . We assign these latter two bands as mixed vibrational modes associated with C-C, C-H, and Si-H vibrations.

Water contact angles were measured using a Ramé-Hart DROPimage CA v2.5 instrument. The modified porous layer with aliphatic alkyl chain hydridosilane reagent was significantly more hydrophobic than either the pSi starting

material or the non-porous Si substrate (See inset of Fig. 1a for water contact angle). SEM images of as-etched pSi and coupling products were obtained with an FEI XL30 UHR (Ultra High Resolution) scanning electron microscope. SEM images demonstrated that the open pore structure was preserved after the surface modification (Fig. 1b).

Steady-state photoluminescence (PL) spectra ($\lambda_{ex} = 385$ nm, UV LED) were obtained using a QE Pro spectrometer (Ocean Optics) fitted with a 460 nm long-pass emission filter. The n-type preparation displays strong photoluminescence (PL) immediately after electrochemical etching, when the surface is terminated with silicon hydride species, but chemical reactions with this type of surface often lead to loss of photoluminescence due to the generation of non-radiative carrier traps. However, the coupling products have been found to passivate the surface and preserve photoluminescence from pSi.

Figure 1: (a) ATR-FTIR spectra of as-etched pSi and coupling product. Inset: water contact angle. (b) SEM images of coupling product. Scale bar: 100 nm.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Dehydrogenative coupling of alkyl-hydrosilanes provides a mild, efficient, and experimentally convenient means to attach Si-C bonded species to hydrogen-terminated Si surfaces. Unlike the C=C species used to graft organics to Si-H surfaces via the hydrosilylation reaction, the reactive-SiH₃ species used in dehydrogenative coupling reacts with traces of adventitious water or oxygen, avoiding the oxidative side reactions at the Si-H surface that lead to reduced yield and inefficient attachment. The chemistry proceeds via Si-Si bond formation, which yields chemically stable surfaces that preserve photoluminescence from quantum-confined Si domains in the porous Si matrix.

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